

PROBLEMS OF ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION

Scientific and technical journal

e-ISSN: 2901-7845 (ISSN: 2091-5004)

2026, VOLUME-04, ISSUE-02.

The journal is included in the list of scientific journals in which scientific articles on technical sciences (construction, mechanics and machine building) and architecture are subject to publication by the decision of the OAK Board (certificate No. 00757, 2000.31.01). It is hereby notified that the articles published in English in our journal are equated to scientific articles published in foreign scientific publications in accordance with the decision of the OAK

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ASSESSMENT AND FORECASTING OF VEHICLE TRAFFIC FLOW ENTERING URGENCH CITY

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Improving the throughput capacity of urban road networks, proper organization of traffic, and ensuring road safety are among the most pressing issues in the world today. This includes the growth of traffic flows and congestion in various regions and cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Examining all transport flow-related issues in our country reveals a variety of underlying causes. The routes for properly organizing vehicle traffic in Urgench city have been analyzed, and relevant proposals and recommendations have been developed.

Keywords: city, street, flow, intensity, intersection, public transport, transport infrastructure, bus.

INTRODUCTION

The development of the automobile industry worldwide, the growing demand for personal vehicles, increased urban mobility, time-saving needs, transport convenience, and the organization of freight and passenger movement are among the key issues in urban planning. The rapid growth of motorization has brought a number of negative consequences for cities, including: road accidents; environmental pollution; traffic congestion; reduction of recreational urban space due to parking areas; and excessive proximity of road networks to historical monuments and structures in historic city centers — resulting in adverse effects (noise, exhaust gases, vibration, electromagnetic radiation, etc.) exceeding established norms, which negatively impact urban residents.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, field observation (empirical) and analytical-mathematical modeling methods were used to determine the intensity of the incoming and outgoing traffic flow in the city of Urgench and to forecast its future state. The research process was carried out in the following stages:

1. *Primary data collection (Field observation method):* To collect data on traffic flow, practical observations were conducted on the D213 (Urgench-Khonka) highway during various peak hours of the day. Data recording was carried out in two different ways:

- Visual (direct) counting method: During the morning peak time (08:00–10:00), vehicles

were directly counted and categorized by observers on site.

- Video surveillance method: During noon (12:00–14:00) and evening (17:00–19:00) peak times, the process of registering flow intensity was recorded using video cameras and then analyzed indoors (desk study).

2. *Data processing and standardization:* Due to the heterogeneous composition of the traffic flow (passenger cars, trucks with various load capacities, buses, etc.), it was necessary to bring the movement intensity to a single standard measure. For this purpose, special equivalent (conversion) coefficients were applied based on urban planning norms and rules (SHNQ 2.07.01-03, Clause 140). All obtained indicators were mathematically modeled in MS Excel software and converted to a single passenger car equivalent unit.

3. *Forecasting method:* To determine the future load on the street and road network of Urgench city, extrapolation and trend-based mathematical forecasting methods were used based on statistical data. Using this method, the growth dynamics of the traffic flow for the next 10 years (2026-2036) were developed.

RESULTS. Assessment and forecasting of vehicle traffic flow entering Urgench city. Urgench, one of the cities of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a population of 149,900, requires the analysis of traffic intensity on its urban road network through experimental research and the

application of mathematical formulas — a pressing need of the modern era.

As in other cities, identifying modern urban planning and engineering solutions to assess incoming and outgoing vehicle traffic flows in Urgench, developing transport infrastructure, and improving the road network remains an ongoing priority. Currently, there are 6 state-level and 2 local-level roads leading into the city.

In order to clarify the main indicators causing congestion on the city’s main road network — particularly the imbalance between incoming and outgoing traffic volumes — a study was conducted in Urgench in 2026. The D213 (Urgench–Khonqa) highway was selected as the research object. Experimental studies were carried out during peak hours, counting vehicles visually during the morning period (08:00–10:00) and via video surveillance during lunch (12:00–14:00) and evening (17:00–19:00) hours, each over a 2-hour period. The following data were obtained (Figures 1.1–1.2).

As shown in Figure 1.1, the largest share of vehicle traffic entering Urgench throughout

the day comes via the D213 (Urgench–Khonqa) highway. The highest flow was observed during the evening peak hour compared to the morning peak, while midday flow was found to be considerably lower than either peak period.

Figure 1.1. Number of vehicles entering Urgench city. (vehicles / 2 hours)

The highest number of outgoing vehicles from Urgench was recorded during the morning peak hour on the D213 (Urgench–Khonka) highway, and the same road again showed the highest

◆ D213 (Urgench-Khonka) highway

figures during the evening peak period.

Figure

1.2. Number of vehicles departing Urgench city (vehicles / 2 hours)

Results of experimental studies conducted in spring (Table 1.1). Number of vehicles entering Urgench city (vehicles / 2 hours)

◆ D213 (Urgench-Khonka) highway

Table 1.1

№	Road name	Traffic intensity count sheet									
		Count period	Truck ≤2t	Truck 2-5t	Truck 5-8t	Truck >8t	Trailer / Semi-trailer	Bus	Trolleybus	Moto / Moped	Passenger car
1	D213 (Urganch-Khonka)	8:00-10:00	60	8	4	2	7	8	0	6	1012
		12:00-14:00	86	30	8	8	0	4	0	2	952
		17:00-19:00	58	12	14	4	12	14	0	12	1016

Before calculating the traffic intensity of incoming flows, different vehicle types must be converted to passenger car units (PCU) using the following coefficients: passenger cars – 1.0; trucks by load capacity (t): up to 2.0 – 1.5; 2.0 to 5 – 2.0; 5 to 8 – 2.5; over 8 – 3.5; trailers and semi-trailers – 3.5; buses – 2.5; trolleybuses – 3.0; motorcycles and mopeds – 0.5.

Taking the above into account, a conversion table to passenger car equivalent was compiled using Excel formulas (Table 1.2).

Vehicles entering Urgench city converted to passenger car units

Table 1.2

№	Road name	PCU conversion coefficients per SHNQ 2.07.01-03, Clause 140										Total PCU
		Count period	Passenger car	Truck ≤2t	Truck 2-5t	Truck 5-8t	Truck >8t	Trailer / Semi-trailer	Bus	Trolleybus	Moto / Moped	
				1,5	2	2,5	3	3,5	2,5	3	0,5	
1	D213 (Urganch-Khonka)	8:00-10:00	1012	60	8	10	6	24,5	20	0	3	11
		12:00-14:00	952	129	60	20	24	0	10	0	1	44
		17:00-19:00	1016	87	24	35	12	42	35	0	6	11
												12
												57

Based on forecast calculations, the projected traffic model for all vehicle flows entering Urgench city (Figure 1.3) shows that the average annual daily traffic intensity is expected to increase by 63% over the next 10 years.

Figure 1.3. Projected average annual daily traffic intensity of vehicles entering Urgench city

CONCLUSION. To prevent traffic congestion in Urgench city, it is necessary to improve the public transport system, establish dedicated bus lanes, and develop a separate system for unscheduled taxis and passenger vehicles. One of the main causes of peak-hour congestion in the city is the narrowness of roads and the insufficient number of bridges. To improve traffic flow, the construction of underpasses and overpasses is essential.

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